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INDIVIDUAL APPROACHES TO EVENTS IN AZERBAIJANI AND GERMAN EMIGRATION LITERATURE AND THEIR COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

In this article, the author talked about individual approaches to events in Azerbaijani and German emigration literature and their comparative analysis. Having an important influence on the development of Marxist literary studies, including the literary process of his time, both in Germany and abroad, Franz Mehring also played an important role in the formation of social and political opinion. This influence was also great because Mehring was a well-known historian of the Prussian state and its labor movement, the most talented publicist of the left wing of German social democracy, one of the founders of "Spartak" and the union of the Communist Party of Germany. As the author notes, all progressive German writers looked optimistically at the future and believed that humanity would accept democracy and civilized life as a vital necessity.

Research scientist Nikbur Jabbarli writes: "Azerbaijani emigration literature is a phenomenon of the 20th century. In other words, it is the literature created by our emigrant writers, poets, playwrights and literary studies that were in open and uncompromising opposition to the totalitarian Soviet regime between 1920 and 1991. The national independence movement carried out by our political emigration-" It is an important component and ideological front of the "Azerbaijan cause". Azerbaijani emigration literature is based on the ideology of Azerbaijanis and is a nationalist, Turkic, patriotic, independence, populist, libertarian and republican literature. Prominent representatives of Azerbaijani emigration literature have always kept alive the national ideal and national consciousness in their scientific, literary and artistic creations, regardless of where they were in the world, they did not turn back or retreat from their occupations even for a moment or a step; they fought until their last breath.

Keywords: individual approaches, emigration literature, progressive German writers, national ideal, ideological front.

Having an important influence on the development of Marxist literary studies, including the literary process of his time, both in Germany and abroad, Franz Mehring also played an important role in the formation of social and political opinion. This influence was also great because Mehring was a well-known historian of the Prussian state and its labor movement, the most talented publicist of the left wing of German social democracy, one of the founders of "Spartak" and the union of the Communist Party of Germany. Friedrich Engels, V. I. Lenin, Rosa Luxemburg, Wilhelm Peak and others, who were Marxist scientists and prominent political figures, highly valued this and acknowledged it many times. But Mehring remained a child of his time, like many prominent comrades-in-arms of ideas. There were deep hesitations and upheavals in his outlook and political beliefs. In the Marxist thought of Mehring, there were deviations and errors of ideas arising from the specific aspects of his time. These ideas were thoroughly analyzed and researched in the USSR and beyond, as well as in the works of Lucas, Schiller and other literary critics. At the same time, Mehring's works were misrepresented by a number of reviewers. Undoubtedly, such a complex issue as Mehring's huge idea and thought, socio-politically oriented talent could understand the society and structure could not be fully understood in his time. His researchers were not ready or able to understand Mehring as a whole. Mehring's first struggle with public life started with his family when he was still a student. Mehring resisted and fought as much as he could when his parents, who had conservative views, put pressure on him. His parents

were well-known radical representatives of German bourgeois democracy. Mehring's struggle with his parents actually marked the beginning of the struggle with the German social structure of that time. [8]

From 1867 to 1971, Mehring started working in the newspaper "Die Zeitung" published in Berlin. In 1974-1975, he collaborated with the popular weekly literary-philosophical magazine "Die Waage". These magazines were headed by Hugo Weiss. During the years he worked in these bodies, Mehring also tried to study the essence of bourgeois-democratic journalism, its weak and strong points in a comparative way. Johann Jacobi, who was a philosopher and doctor by profession, unconditionally promoted and encouraged the German revolution and journalism during these years. At the same time, he had recently started sharply criticizing Bismarck's domestic and foreign policy. Working hard to build his own party, Jacobi advocated a fair division of production between labor and capital as the main program of his party. The utopianism of this program did not bring Jacobi any success in politics. Towards the end of his life, he became a non-party leader and began giving speeches in favor of the leaders of the Social Democrats. These speeches were appreciated by Maris and later by V. I. Lenin, but radical changes did not occur in Jacobin's mind. However, his ideas were carefully studied and studied by open-minded people of his time. Undoubtedly, these bold speeches of Jacobin could not remain unnoticed by Franz Mehring, who had just entered the literary and political life. His early publicist was formed under the influence of Jacobi, Keys Lossalu's philosophical, ethical-social thoughts and

worldviews. This influence was clearly felt in the political articles and essays he published in many media outlets during that period. In particular, the socio-political views of the young Franz Mehring were clearly reflected in the "Treichko" pamphlet. In this pamphlet, Mehring denied the antagonistic class struggle. Following Lossal, he affirmed that a fair distribution of national wealth can be achieved through the socialist state structure. Like Lossal, Mehring also considered the path of bourgeois moral education and scientific education of the working class as the basis for building socialism. Mehring devoted a special place to fiction and philosophy in solving these issues. There is no doubt that idealism had a fundamental place in his public views during his first period of journalism. Mehring considered the moral principles of the state and people with it as a historical driving force. In his article published in "Terazi" magazine, the development of the Prussian state and the path of this development were the main topic. Mehring saw the strength of this state in the personal qualities of the enlightened monarch Frederick II. [9]

Mehring's historical-literary-critical article published in "Duvaq" magazine, it was believed that the German bourgeoisie could still return to the humanist ideals of the 18th century and the revolutionary efforts of 1948. For comparison, he saw these ideal efforts as native, alongside politics and literature as Double Wings. For him, more classical literature was a great social force. At the end of the aforementioned summary, Mehring came to such a conclusion, which is typical for Mehring's worldview, that "there is an irresistible infatuation in all areas of our poetic literature, which is this pure and faithful mirror of the people's soul, but sooner or later a time will come when we will see that how many losses we have made in our spiritual life". [7]

Mehring noted with particular rebellion that the cruelest judgment will be the stumbling of our literature against the founders of this empire, who did nothing for the great writers and philosophers who worked for the integrity of free Germany. In 1884-1885, Mehring got close to the bourgeois-democrats again and collaborated in their magazine "Demokratische Blatter".

As one of all the progressive German writers, Mehring also looked optimistically at the future, and he sincerely believed that humanity would accept democracy and a civilized way of life as a vital necessity. In the center of his creativity, as in the case of his fellow writer German Hesse, there was a person, his destiny, and the attempts made on the way to perfection. Although Mehring entered the circle of social and political life of the German people, he could not conquer their spirituality. [5]

The political articles of Klara Setkin, a member of the German and international communist movement, one of the founders of the German Communist Party, attracted the attention of progressive intellectuals as a poetic mirror of her time. He joined the revolutionary movement in the late 1970s. In 1881, he joined the German Social Democratic Party. K. Setkini, who was forced to live in exile during the period when the exceptional law against socialists was in force (1878-

1890), took an active part in the socialist movements of France, Austria and Italy. K. Setkin played an important role in the preparation of the founding congress of the II International (Paris, 1889). She returned to her homeland in 1890 and headed the Social Democratic women's movement in Germany. This brave man, who was an uncompromising fighter against the supremacy of man over man throughout his life, melted his conscious life like a candle in the path of happiness, freedom and progress of his people. K. Setkin was a great citizen. Despite all the mistakes in his social and political views, he sincerely believed that humanity would be saved by the socialist revolutionary ideas and the realization of this revolution.

It is no coincidence that he was among those who warmly welcomed the first Russian revolution. On the other hand, K. Setkin was appreciated by the progressive people of the world, well-known political figures, and his activity was highly appreciated. K. Setkin was elected to the International Women's Secretariat at the First International Women's Conference (1907) held on her own initiative. Again, the International Copenhagen Conference (1910) initiated by her decided to celebrate March 8 as International Women's Day every year. K. Setkin, who was arrested for his revolutionary activity in 1915, continued his revolutionary work even after his release from prison. He was widely active as one of the leaders of the "Spartacus alliance". [6]

After the German Communist Party was established, K. Setkin, who was elected a member of the Central Committee of the party (1919), welcomed the victory of the Great October Socialist Revolution in Russia with special joy. Of course, K. Setkin, one of the invincible fighters of his people and era, as well as the political movement he belonged to, as one of tens of thousands of colleagues, was unaware of the terrible end of the socialist revolution, which would bring disaster to millions of people. It was necessary to experience this new era in order to fully understand the essence of this revolution, which was sprouting in the womb and would drag humanity into the Bolshevik vortex in the coming years.

After the fall of the Soviet government, as the inside of the archives were opened, it would become clear to the world community that the scenario of the revolution under the leadership of V.I. Lenin was actually prepared and implemented by German intelligence in the German political circles and headquarters of Germany, where K. Setkin and his comrades-in-arms lived and fought. . K. Setkin and thousands of his comrades-in-arms and ideological friends are helping to establish an evil, satanic structure without even knowing it. Progressive humanity, including K. Setkin's own country, Germany, would have to fight for exactly 70 years to destroy this nest of evil, Bolshevism, the Bolshevik structure, which hangs over the head of free thought like a nightmare. Naturally, K. Setkin, like his co-conspirators, could not fully understand that the Communist Party's usurpation of power in 1917 actually laid the foundation of an ideological state. With this, Bolshevik oppression, Bolshevik terror, tyranny, which is the other side of fascism, begins and continues. The Communist Party of Russia (Bolsheviks), which was

never officially registered anywhere, took a monopolistic position, looking for terrible experiments, rejecting any different ideas. This party considers its role in managing the state "irreplaceable", such a situation led to the establishment of a totalitarian regime (system). Like his comrades-in-arms, K. Setkin could not understand that exclusion of one-parties and pluralism opens the way for the authorities to cause social problems. [4]

Those who supported the socialist revolution forgot that monopoly in any field is inherently oppressive; it operates from a selfish, narrow perspective. They forgot that in a socialist society, the "exploitation of man by man" is stopped, there are neither poor nor rich - the idea that everyone can benefit equally from the achievements of the society was actually an empty, false rhetoric. [10]

In opposition to the existing regime in Germany, the progressive revolutionaries who hailed the Great October Socialist Revolution and urged humanity to follow this path could not see that Soviet citizens were actually living without knowledge of "human rights". The point is that years later in 1948, even after the UN adopted the "general declaration of human rights", the Soviet government did not allow this declaration to be distributed in the USSR. As a rule, the Soviet state signed international documents, but in reality it did not follow the laws. The principle was the same - "sign, start over". Many types of information were classified in the Soviet state. Gradually it became extreme. "The lying, sloganeering propagandist communist press was in the grip of censorship. Socialist literary works were not exempt from this control. Humor and satire were in the frame. Every republic had a satirical magazine, and satirical criticism was given in doses. The Central "Krokodil" magazine had a circulation of 10 million. Everyone was equally funny." The role of three slogans in the coming to power of the Communists under Lenin's leadership was attractive to the masses: exit from the World War; distribute land to villagers; to hand over factories and plants to the workers. Undoubtedly, like all progressive-minded people, Clara Setkin was attracted by these principles promised by the Great October Socialist Revolution, and she sincerely believed that the socialist revolution would bring happiness and happiness to people. [5]

K. Setkin, who was in Baku on October 20-21, 1929, got acquainted with the activities of the Women's Club named after Ali Bayramov at that time, and participated in the joint meeting of the Baku Soviet and AHISH. In the book he later wrote "In the Free Caucasus", he spoke extensively about his impressions of Azerbaijan. Klara Setkin regularly appeared in the magazine "Eastern Woman" with her socio-political articles. [2]

When we look at our contemporary life through the eyes of the current social structure, we must admit that K.Setkin led a contrasting, but extremely honest life for his time. The way of life of such people, their struggle, whichever way you look at it, first of all serves the democratic advancement of humanity and the humanization of society. Undoubtedly, the Soviet functionaries knew well how to hide the chauvinist face of a place called the USSR from the eyes of a fighter like

K. Setkin. It is not difficult to divert the attention of thousands of such people who have a romantic view of the democratization of society in a system where the Soviet military machine and the Soviet propaganda machine work side by side with the dreams of a beautiful future and glorious communism. Klara Setkin and her comrades-in-arms were right that indeed Nazi Germany was approaching the vortex of fascism in an unimaginable way, and every progressive German person who felt the prejudice of his people and nation was absolutely right to seek a way out of this danger. It was in the face of such a difficult situation that the brilliance of socialism and the Great October Revolution attracted progressive people as a way of salvation, a door to salvation. The feelings of people deeply rooted in the ideas of freedom and democracy echoed with the populist slogans that were widespread in the Soviet Union. No matter how misguided these voices were, they essentially served humanity, democracy and freedom. [11]

R. Luxemburg, who was an active member of the German, Polish and international labor movement with revolutionary articles and speeches, one of the leaders and theoreticians of the left radical trend in the Polish and German social-democratic movement, and at the same time internationally, one of the founders of the German Communist Party, is as contradictory as K. Setkin. He lived a long life and died tragically. Luxemburg, who joined the secret revolutionary movement from a young age, immigrated to Switzerland in 1889, and moved to Germany in 1898. Luxemburg, which opened its eyes to the world in a Jewish bourgeois family. In Germany, he joined the German social-democratic movement, took a position on its left wing, and fought decisively against the revisionism of E. Bernitein. Since he did not understand Lenin's principle of creating a new proletarian party, he criticized the Bolsheviks in 1904 due to the split of the RSDFP, but soon after welcoming the Russian revolution of 1905-1907, he came close to the Bolsheviks in many issues of the strategy and tactics of the revolutionary struggle. [3]

V.I.Lenin highly appreciated his pamphlet "Mass Strike, Party and Trade Unions", which he wrote in Finland in the summer of 1906. The work summarized the experience of the first Russian revolution and defined the tasks of the German labor movement.

Luxemburg, together with V. I. Lenin, amended A. Bebel's resolution on the issue of imperialist war and attitude to imperialism, pointed out the imperialist character of the First World War, and sharply criticized the chauvinist policy of the social-democratic leaders. Rosa Luxemburg, one of the founders of the "Spartacus Union", was highly appreciated despite her many mistakes (denying the possibility of national liberation wars during imperialism, the right of nations to self-determination, etc.). R. Luxemburg, who was imprisoned for 4 years for his revolutionary activities, was arrested on January 15, 1919 by the conspiracy of the counter-revolutionaries after the Berlin workers' strike was suppressed, and was brutally killed together with his comrade-in-arms, K. Liebknecht. As an ardent propagator of L. Tolstoy's work, he always called humanity for peace. [8]

Karl Liebknecht, the figure of the German and international labor movement, one of the founders of the German Communist Party, son of Wilhelm Liebknecht, was also one of the tireless fighters for the freedom of his people.

Together with R. Luxemburg, he was one of the founders of the "Spartak Union" and one of the organizers of the publication of the "Rote Fans" newspaper. He was sentenced to hard labor for 4 years in May 1915 for exposing the ruling forces in his works and the process of political struggle, but was released from prison due to public pressure. Liebknecht, who played an important role in the development of the Marxist bridge, liked the slogan of the Bolsheviks to turn the imperialist war into a civil war starting from 1915 and consistently defended this position in his political articles. At the instigation of the reactionary forces, he was also arrested and brutally murdered. [1]

Karl Liebknecht's work "militarism and anti-imperialism" analyzes the chauvinist nature of militarism leading to fascism in the smallest details, and the idea of the united front of the progressive world against imperialism was irreversibly promoted. When talking about Azerbaijani emigration literature, it is necessary to talk about the work "Ali and Nino" and its author Gurban Said. The novel "Ali and Nino", first published in German in 1937 and widely distributed in Europe has been translated and published in 27 languages.

However, since Gurban Said is one of the author's signatures, his identity has been disputed. Many writers have said that this work belongs to the pen of Y.V. Chamanzaminli. The reason for this was Y. Vazir's exile in Europe in the 20s, and on the other hand, the closeness of form and style of the novel "Ali and Nino" to his works, and the author's familiarity with the history of Azerbaijan and the political events there. [11] However, there are facts that confirm that the novel "Ali and Nino" does not belong to Yusif Vazir. Thus, since a long time, the signatures of Gurban Said and Asad Bey have been mentioned as belonging to Leo Nussembaum, who left Azerbaijan after the events of April 1920 and was a Jew by nationality. This fact was confirmed in the letter dated June 10, 1974, written by Mrs. Elfride Ehrenfels, the publisher of the novel "Ali and Nino" to Turkologist Ahmed Shmide, who lives in Germany, in the personal archive of professor Tofiq Huseynov, one of the researchers of Chamanzaminli heritage. The text of that letter was given as a corroborating fact in the foreword of the translation of "Allahu Akbar. The Fall and Rise of the Islamic World from Abdul Hamid to Ibn Saud" by Mohammad Asad Bey, candidate of philological sciences of Circassian Gurbanli, together with Wolfgang von Weiss: [3]

"Dear Mr. Schmide. I want to inform you - the translator and interpreter of Turkish languages who traveled to Baku, that Gurban Said was the pen name of Muhammad Asad Bey from Baku. I worked together

with him in Vienna in 1938 on the publication of his novel "The Girl from the Bay". Sincerely, Signature: Elfride Ehrenfels. 14 titles of Leo Nussembaum, whose works were published under the signatures of Muhammad Asad Bey and Gurban Said, are listed in German libraries. These books, published in 1932-1938, are the product of hard work. [4]

Research scientist Nikbur Jabbarli writes: "Azerbaijani emigration literature is a phenomenon of the 20th century. To be more specific, the chronological boundaries of this literature cover the years 1920-1921, that is, the period after the fall of the Azerbaijan People's Republic until the restoration of the independence of the Republic of Azerbaijan. That is, 1920-1991 It is the literature created by our emigrant writer, poet, dramatist, who was in open and uncompromising opposition to the totalitarian Soviet regime between the years 1980 and 1990. It is an important component and ideological front of the national independence movement of our political emigration and is a nationalist, Turkic, patriotic, independence, folk, libertarian and republican literature". [1]

Yes, the outstanding representatives of Azerbaijani emigration literature, whose names have been mentioned many times above, have always kept alive the national ideal and national consciousness in their scientific, literary and artistic creations, regardless of where they were in the world, they did not turn back from their occupations even for a moment or a step, and they fought until their last breath. They took May their souls rest in peace, because their efforts and sufferings were not in vain!!!

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